

FEATURES OF THE USE OF PROFILING BY CUSTOMS OFFICERS

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Annotation This article covers the organization and specifics of the effectiveness of the use of profiling by customs authorities in ensuring security in developed countries. It also provides theoretical information on the history, necessity and field of application of the origin of the profiling method.

Keywords: profiling, psychological portrait, psychological observation, survey, criminal profiling, transport profiling.

Introduction

"Profayling "is English for" profile " - profile, disguise. Profiling is a method of truthful assessment, prediction of an individual's actions by assessing their nonverbal behavior and specifics.

The profiling method is a method of creating a personality profile that allows you to predict individuals from the beginning using several psychological methods, such as psychological assessment, observation, analysis of changes in their behavior on the basis of their appearance and behavior.

The founders of the profail method are psychologist scientists P.Ekman, W. Frizen, M. Suckerman and B. Are considered De Paulo. In 2012, the. The criminal profiling method was presented by Spiritsa at the International Academy for the study of lies.

In his opinion: criminal profiling is understood as the compilation of his psychological profile using complex methods that diagnose the characteristics of a person who is assumed to be a criminal.

Profiling is psychological portraiture. One of those who attempted to compose a psychological portrait in 1888 is the British surgeon Thomas Bond.

The experience of this profiling method has been improving for several years in countries such as Israel, the United States, Russia. The profiling method is made up of two complementary methods, the psychological observation and survey(interview) method.

Profiling accepts its content - fast psychodiagnostics, emotion analysis, manipulative techniques, hypno technology, vocabulary, graphology, facial expression analysis, muscle activity analysis, and Social Psychology.

Also, the introduction in the activities of employees of customs authorities is effective in professional monitoring, environmental analysis, identification of signs of people's behavior, suspicion, solving problems that arise with citizens during service hours. Individuals involved in profiling are usually referred to as profilers.

The following can be recognized as the object of profiler's study:

- mimesis;
- gestures;
- characteristic features of behavior;
- psycholinguistic laws of speech;
- paralinguistic symptoms of verbal communication, etc.

Any information is given only through the system of signs, or rather, signs. There are a number of character systems used in the communicative process, to which, in a suitable way, the tools used in the communication process can be classified. The means of speech and non-speech communication are distinguished. In the profiling method, the description of verbal and nonverbal means of communication is of great importance.

Psychological means of communication to two:

- 1.verbal
- 2.divided into nonverbal forms and covering:
 - oral speech;

- written speech;
- mimes;
- pantomimics.

Speech communication is the most universal means of communication. Consequently, through speech, the content of information is given almost completely. Through Verbal communication, the individual is able to freely state his or her feedback. In the activities of employees of customs authorities, the use of speech means of communication plays an extremely important role. The effectiveness of the employee's service activities largely depends on the correct expression of his thoughts in the process of direct communication or the formation of various documents, their correct statement.

While speech is a universal means of communication, it becomes relevant only in conditions that are involved in the activity system, while activity immunity is complemented by the use of other-non - speech means of communication. The first group of these tools includes gestures and facial expressions.

Facial expressions are dynamic expressions of the face at the moment of communication. A gesture (gesture) is a gesture developed in society and representing a state of mind. Looking at them, we draw conclusions about the attitude of a person to something, to a person, to something. A gesture can signal a person's desires, his condition. Actions of the human body, mediated by facial expressions, gestures, intonations, expressing its psychic state, especially emotions, are called pantomimics. Another group of communication that is part of the non-speech medium is formed by the vocalization system, that is, the sound quality, its range, tone, etc. All these additions increase the importance of information and serve as an "additional" function in specific speech.

The methodological basis of the profiling method is precisely the unusual character of people, some signs of their appearance, behavior, speech tone, pace and characteristic qualities of other Reporting Members.

The phrase profiling first began to be used in the United States in the 1980s. Among the first specialists to work in this field are John Douglas, Robert Ressler. It was under them that the Center for the study of crimes of aggression was established under the Academy of the Federal Bureau of search in 1984.

The center is primarily focused on the prosecution of middle and serious crimes, the study of which, the psychological portrait of criminals, was the first to be investigated.

With the help of the services of the profilers, a number of serious and vakhshian murders were exposed. In it, they achieved these achievements mainly through the study of the behavior of the criminal, the creation of a psychological portrait, the imposition of their own psychological characteristics, the study of motives for committing a crime, and the prediction of their future character.

The main focus on profiling was strengthened after the 2004 terrorist act in Russia. The technology is widely used in the United States, Finland, France, the United Kingdom for the purpose of providing security in public security services in several major European countries, as well as in the state of Israel.

The profiling method has the following properties:

1. One of the features of the profiling method is the observation of the behavior of individuals moving across the border, asking them questions, making Express psychodiagnostics, recording deviations from the norm in their behavior, and other actions aimed at studying them.
2. In profiling's logical scheme, to build a model of the harakats of individuals who may pose a threat during the preparation of illegal interference actions; to identify signs of preparation of such harakats; to create a classification of extemporaneous performers of such harakats.
3. For the implementation of the profiling method, specialists with a high level of training are involved, who have many years of experience in the field of visual psychodiagnostics, diagnostic express-conversation, neuroinguistic programming techniques, investigative activities.

If we study foreign experience in the field of profiling, it can be divided directly according to the following directions:

- criminal profiling-mainly in Europe and the USA. widely implemented;
- profiling in transport-mainly widely practiced in Israel and Russia.

Criminal profiling is usually a direction aimed at studying the behavior of individuals who commit criminal acts. Its methodological basis rests on the "behaviorist" theory of psychology (the study of human behavior). It directly analyzes the motives that generate human actions. Psychologist professionals working in the police system of the United Kingdom, Austria, Germany and other European countries usually provide practical support to employees experienced in exposing murder crimes in this regard.

They psychologically analyze in what style the criminal profiling method carried out unusual actions in the behavior of an individual, the peculiarities of the geographical location of the area, what traces remained on the scene by the person who committed the crime.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, it can be noted that with the help of the profiling method, the employees of the customs authorities can further improve their service activities in the field of security. The advantage of this method is that it can have a complete source of information about a person in a short period of time.

REFERENCES

1. Akramov M. R. et al. Шахс касбий йўналганлиги ривожланишида масъулиятлиликнинг аҳамияти //Молодой ученый. – 2021. – №. 11. – С. 259261.
- 2.Qodirov M.S. Воjхона хизмати ходимлари касбий faoliyatida profayling texnologiyasini rivojlantirish masalalari. // “Zamonaviy ta’lim” jurnali, 2019. № 11..
- 3.Х.Т. Одилқориев, И.Т. Тультеев ва бошқ.; проф. Х.Т. Одилқориев тахрири остида. Давлат ва ҳуқуқ назарияси: Дарслик . Тошкент.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2009. – Б. 296.
4. Qambarova, D. Y. (2022). INTERACTIVE METHODS OF ENGLISH

TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION. Oriental Journal of Education, 2(1), 1-7.

5. Kambarova, D. Y. (2022). THE ROLE OF SPEAKING ACTIVITIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING. Zamonaviy dunyoda pedagogika va psixologiya: Nazariy va amaliy izlanishlar, 1(10), 65-67.

6. Azimbayevna, D. G., & Vohidovna, X. X. (2021). FEATURES IN THE TRANSLATION OF MEDICAL TERMS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(11), 470-474. Advanced Sciences Index Factor ASI Factor = 1.7

7. Abdullaxayevna, A. R. (2022). Developing Students' Knowledge of English Through a Creative Approach. Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History, 5, 5-

8. 4. Профайлинг в деятельности органов внутренних дел: Учебное пособие / Под.пред В.Л.Цветков. – М., 2014. – С.10

9. Профилактика экстремизма в молодежной среде. Проблемы и решения: научно-методический сборник // Под редакцией М.В. Паромоновой. -Иркутск: ФГБОУ ВПО «ВСГАО», 2012 – С.8.